

ENSURING ECONOMIC SECURITY IN THE FORMATION AND GROWTH OF MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY CLUSTERS

Sadriddinova Nigora Khusniddinova

PhD, researcher of Tashkent State University
of Economics, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14963941>

Abstract. This article explores economic security in the creation and expansion of manufacturing industry clusters. These clusters consist of interconnected enterprises, research institutions, and infrastructure facilities, enhancing economic competitiveness and stability. However, without effective economic security measures, clusters may encounter risks that hinder their growth and development.

Keywords: economic security, resource provision, national security, measures to ensure the economic security of industrial clusters.

Despite the fact that the theoretical foundations of clusters were laid in the late 19th century by A. Marshall, and the term "cluster" was introduced into circulation by M. Porter in the 80s of the last century, recently the problems of clustering have attracted active interest, and the formation and development of scientific and industrial clusters is an extremely urgent process, the effective implementation of which is hampered by the emergence of various macro- and mesoeconomic problems. We decomposed the economic problems of the formation and development of scientific and industrial clusters based on structuring clusters as economic systems and identifying the internal environment of the cluster and its external environment.

As A. Skoch notes, increased differentiation is a powerful factor counteracting the development of integration processes. The administration and corporations located in more prosperous regions will always include in their assessment of the effectiveness of integration projects a premium for the risk associated with the possible parasitic mood of integration entities from more backward regions. The significant influence of internal and external factors on the choice of regional development concepts is clearly demonstrated by world experience, briefly discussed below.

In this regard, it is useful to turn to the experience of Germany, where the closest attention is paid to stimulating regional development. Moreover, when choosing objects of state support, preference is given to those enterprises whose activities are not limited to the region, but reach the interregional level. As shown by A.G. Granberg, recipients of incentives must present clear evidence that within three years after the completion of the program to support their

activities, mainly carried out through investments in industrial production and infrastructure, the majority of their products will be sold outside the region. A. Yu. Zudin notes that the cluster approach to the development of the German economy began to be applied in the second half of the 20th century, when multi-industry associations began to form in territorial production complexes, which was a consequence of the effective implementation of the equalization policy aimed at supporting individual regions for the purpose of accelerated development by redistributing federal budget funds in their favor for a certain period of time at the expense of other regions. The objective grounds for pursuing a leveling policy are environmental disasters, economic depression, unfavorable conditions, etc.

In Great Britain, the problem of disproportions in the level of development between municipalities within one county is more acute than between counties as a whole. The regional policy instruments used here also include the provision of investment grants and the stimulation of structural changes in problem regions, consisting in the replacement of enterprises in stagnant sectors of the economy subject to closure with new competitive industries. The analysis of world experience in the formation of regional policy could be continued, since its useful elements can be found in almost any country. But its generalization leads to the conclusion that its main target guidelines are the reduction of differences in the standards of living of the population of the country's regions and the stimulation of regional development. In fact, such goals of regional policy are set in all countries, and the main differences occur in the choice of specific mechanisms for its implementation.

Yu. G. Lavrikova proposed a set of various mechanisms for implementing regional policy that would facilitate the formation and development of scientific and industrial clusters:

- providing transfers depending on the size and social conditions of the population, tax potential;
- implementing special programs for the development of the economy of depressed regions;
- providing investment grants for the creation of new competitive industries and jobs;
- providing additional tax preferences to business entities in backward regions (as, for example, in Italy, in the area of social security by declaring annual tax holidays on social payments when creating new jobs in backward regions);

- creating guarantee funds to attract private investment in the development of regional economies, etc.

An analysis of the main concepts of regional economic policy shows that world and domestic economic science have made a significant contribution to the formation of a systemic understanding of the goals and methods for achieving them. However, although the recommendations contained therein can be adapted to a greater or lesser extent to solving modern problems of regional development, in reality this does not always happen. One of such problems, related to increasing the efficiency of interregional economic integration based on the cluster approach, is the focus of this study. In order to understand in more detail the role of interregional economic integration in eliminating structural imbalances in the development of regions and ensuring their strategic competitiveness, modern trends in regional development in Uzbekistan and the place of integration processes in the system of regional economic policy measures are studied.

The main economic problems of the formation and development of scientific and industrial clusters in the region are:

- 1) the depression of the region;
- 2) the lack of expression of territorial specialization (lack of competitive industries and industries);
- 3) underdevelopment of the organizational and legal infrastructure;
- 4) low efficiency of enterprises located in the region (lack of anchor enterprises);
- 5) low scientific potential of the territory.

In conclusion, economic security is a key element of sustainable operation and development of industrial clusters. Effective risk management and creation of favorable conditions for enterprises ensure stability, innovation and competitiveness of industry in the context of global challenges

References:

1. Pilipenko I.V. Competitiveness of countries and regions in the world economy: theory, experience of small countries of Western and Northern Europe. - Smolensk: Oikumena, 2005. - 496 p.
2. Voinarenko M.P. Cluster models of enterprise association in Ukraine / M.P. Voinarenko // Economic revival of Russia. - 2007. - No. 2 (12). - P. 62-86.
3. In the book. Asaul A.N. Methodological aspects of formation and development of entrepreneurial networks / A.N. Asaul, E.G. Skumatov, G.E. Lokteeva / Ed. by prof. A.N. Asaul. - St. Petersburg: Humanitarianism, 2004. - 256 p.

4. Development of clusters: essence, current approaches, foreign experience /
auth. comp. S.F. Pyatinkin, T.P. Bykova. - Minsk: Business and Finance, 2008. -
Pp. 13-14. - 223 p.